

Department of Political Science

**NON-EUROPEAN IMMIGRANTS' INTEGRATION
IN THE SWEDISH SOCIETY AND LABOUR MARKET**

A Dynamic and Two-Way Process

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Abstract

This explorative qualitative study aims to explore how both non-European immigrants ⁽¹⁾ in Sweden and Swedes ⁽²⁾ perceive the obstacles that prevent non-European immigrant integration into the Swedish society and labour market. The bulk of existing research studying non-European immigrants' integration into the European host societies focuses either on integration from the host community's perspective or on challenges migrants face in the host society to be integrated. There are less studies that consider both perspectives (host and migrant) in one study. This study used the Bosswick and Heckmann's (2006) four dimensions of social integration as a theoretical framework to explore how non-European immigrants and Swedes -the two parties in the interactive integration process- perceive integration as a concept and as two-way process. In this study, interviews are conducted with 25 respondents, 9 Swedes and 16 non-European immigrants in Sweden. This study emphasizes the significance of personal contacts for non-European immigrant to enter the Swedish labour market, and the importance of interactive integration into the Swedish Society that allow them to obtain such personal contacts. The results show that respondents - non-European immigrants and Swedes- perceive the concept of *integration* as a two-way process in various ways according to the four theoretical dimensions of social integration.

Keywords: Migration, Non-European immigration, Sweden, Social Integration, Labour Market.

(1) Non-European immigrant in Sweden in this study is a person who moved to Sweden from Asia, Africa and the Middle East as a refugee, family reunification/ love, student or with work visa

(2) Swede in this study is a person who born and raised in Sweden and one or both of his/her parents are born and raised in Sweden also.

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1. Introduction

The European Integration policy defines integration as “*a dynamic, two-way process of mutual accommodation by all immigrants and residents of member states*” stressing that immigrants need to have basic knowledge of the host society’s language, history, and institutions with respect for the basic values of the European Union (EU) (European Integration and Migration Policy, 2014). Immigration can have both positive and negative impacts on the host society. The negative impacts may include a financial burden on municipal budgets, fear of immigrant challenge to local culture, and tensions between native population and migrants because of the competition for housing and/or jobs. On the other side, positive impacts may include immigration contribution to both the local labour market and stabilizing or increasing local population figures (Søholta, Stenbackab & Nørgaard,2018). Migration in Sweden is seen as an essential instrument for addressing certain problems such as demographic ageing and labor shortages (Anthias et al. 2013). Sweden as a social-democratic welfare state- is known for its high intake of refugees. The Swedish migration and integration policies are often linked to the rights-based model (Koopmans 2010). In Sweden, refugees can receive government assistance and they are allowed to self-settle in any municipality across the country (Søholta, Stenbackab & Nørgaard,2018). Sweden has traditionally been known for respecting human rights and multiculturalism through opening doors for refugees which were so-called ‘*Swedish exceptionalism*’ (Dahlstedt & Neergaard, 2019). However, recent trends show that traditional Swedish integration policies have been highly debated within the society in the last decade. Since 2011, immigration and integration issues have been at the top of the political agenda in Sweden. Before 2011, the political institutions in Sweden were largely silent, despite the isolation of large immigrant populations. But this situation of negligence was finally no longer acceptable. Two dramatic events at the end of 2010 have led to this awakening, 1) the entry of the Sweden Democrats party into the Swedish Parliament and 2) the suicide bombing in downtown Stockholm during Christmas days (Heinö, 2011). In the last five years, integration has become a more urgent issue, especially, when Sweden received a huge number of refugees in 2015. According to an online survey was conducted by Pew Research Center in 2016 (comprising of 12,646 respondents in 12 countries), 40% of Swedes believe that refugees do not integrate into society, and 15% of them see refugees as a threat to their country (d’Haenens, Joris, & Heinderyckx, 2019). These results highlight the social gap between Swedes and non-European immigrants. In addition to consideration of social integration, this thesis aims to explore the non-European immigrant integration into the Swedish labor market as well. This

study assumes reciprocal effect between non-European immigrants' integration into the Swedish labor market and their daily social interaction with Swedes. Personal contacts help immigrants to get jobs. Immigrants benefit more from having personal contact with natives than foreign-born people, especially if social contact occurs at the workplace (Petersson, 2014). On the other hand, Integration into the Swedish labor market is the most effective means to improve long-term integration into society, however, the Swedish labor market offers non-European immigrants limited opportunities despite their previous work experience and educational background. Some Non-European immigrants need to study extra courses and even to change their own profession to get place in the Swedish labor market. Studies have shown that non-European immigrants feel that they are not welcomed in Sweden due to their ethnic, religious, or cultural background (Bursell, 2012). Some migrants even change their names to avoid discrimination in the labor market as well (ibid, 2012). The proportion of non-European immigrants and their representation in the Swedish labor market can be an indicator of their integration into society, however, according to Statistics Sweden SCB, the unemployment rate in 2019 was (15.1%) among non-European immigrants born outside Sweden when it was (4.4 %) among native Swedes (SCB, 2019).

1.1 Aim and Research Question

1.1.1 Aim of the study

The aim of this study is to initiate a research on non-European immigrants' integration in Sweden. To do so, the study needs an index that measures policies to integrate migrants in host societies. This study adopts Migration Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) that measures policies to integrate migrants in countries across five continents. According to (MIPEX), Sweden has the highest score (MIPEX, 2020). At this point, a question arises: If Sweden really has such a successful integration policy, why do non-European immigrants feel that they are not socially integrated into the Swedish society? Why do most non-European immigrants live in semi-isolated suburbs in the Swedish big cities Stockholm, Gothenburg and Malmö despite that Sweden is known for a generous welcoming policy? D'Haenens, Joris, & Heinderyckx, (2019) explore attitudes toward migrants and refugees in Western Europe with a focus on Sweden and Belgium. They collect data from The European Social Survey (ESS), Pew Research Center, Ipsos MORI Market research company. In the ESS survey ⁽³⁾, they find that 21% of Swedes think that refugees will take their jobs. In their study, d'Haenens, Joris, & 21%

(3) ESS survey was conducted in 2014-15, 2,000 persons participated in each of 22 countries.

of Swedes think that refugees will take their jobs. In their study, d’Haenens, Joris, & Heinderyckx, (2019) highlight results from an online survey conducted by the Pew Research Center ⁽⁴⁾ shows that 40% of Swedes believe that refugees do not integrate into society, and 15% of them see refugees as a threat to their country. Another telephone survey ⁽⁵⁾ was conducted in 2016 by the Pew Research Center also, showed that 24% of Swedes see refugees as a threat to their country and 57% of them believe that refugees increase terrorism likelihood. This study claims that such results may not reflect reality of immigrant integration in Sweden, although they provide some indications about immigrant integration in Sweden from the Swedish point of view. The purpose of this study is to analyze Swedes and non-European immigrant's perceptions on integration issues related to identity, the labour market and social life in Sweden.

1.1.2 Research Question and Sub questions

How do non-European immigrants and Swedes perceive the challenges and opportunities of non-European immigrants' integration into the Swedish labor market and society?

Three Sub questions:

- ***The Social Identification***

How do both non-European immigrants and Swedes perceive the concept of ‘integration’ and being ‘Swedish’?

- ***Integration into the labor market***

How non-European immigrants and Swedes describe obstacles that hinder non-European immigrants' integration into the Swedish labor market?

- ***Integration into the society***

How non-European immigrants and Swedes perceive obstacles hindering their social interaction integration?

(4) Pew Research Center conducted an online survey in 2016, 12,646 persons participated in 12 countries.

(5) Pew Research Center conducted telephone survey/interviews in 2016, 1000 persons participated in each of 10 countries.

2. Previous Research and Research Gap and study contribution

2.1 Previous Research

Integration issues are discussed everywhere in each country in Europe. A massive amount of research is devoted to study and examine integration issues (Heinö, 2011). Some studies focus on integration from host society perspective and other hand, more research study integration at immigrants' side (what challenge their socio-economic integration) and less from immigrants' perspective.

2.1.1 *Integration literature – host society*

Studies that focus on integration from host society perspective examine immigrants' roles in co-producing local resilience and how do host society links immigration to the local resilience (Søholta, Stenbackab, Nørgaard, 2018), evaluate the integration policy and related political debate in the host society (Heinö, 2011) or assess obligatory integration in which migrants need to acquire language skills and 'norm adherence' to be eligible for permanent residency or citizenship (Goodman and Wright, 2015).

- Using case studies among rural elites in Norway, Sweden, and Denmark, Søholta, Stenbackab and Nørgaard (2018) examine how do Nordic rural elites link immigration to rural resilience, and what characterizes their perspective about immigrants' roles in co-producing rural resilience. Søholta, Stenbackab and Nørgaard (2018) focus on both structural and social integration, welfare, networks, and participation that are essential factors for building local resilience in the host society. The study explores the similarities and differences in how Nordic rural elites perceive immigration in relation to local resilience. Søholta, Stenbackab and Nørgaard (2018) focus on the pragmatic argument expressed by rural elites in Sweden, Denmark and Norway that emphasizes how immigration contributes to population growth – or by minimizing a long-term trend of population decline. The study shows that rural elites value immigrants contributing to economic regional development, rather than in terms of cultural and ethnic diversity. According to Søholt, Stenbacka, and Nørgaard (2018), immigration has become the main source of population increase in the Nordic countries. They shed light on conditioned receptiveness by the rural elites who expect immigrants to become 'co-producers' for local resilience. The authors apply dual concepts of retention vs. receptiveness and exclusion vs. inclusion and find that rural elites relate differently to immigration and local resilience and immigrants are considered valuable for both the local economy, and for population growth (Søholta, Stenbackab and Nørgaard, 2018).

By distinguishing the concepts of inclusion and exclusion, Søholta, Stenbackab and Nørgaard, (2018) find that inclusion in rural places requires more than having a job. Immigrants should be recognized as individuals even though they might be challenging the perception of 'local normality'. According to Søholta, Stenbackab and Nørgaard, (2018), Sweden has had the most liberal immigration policy and Denmark the most restrictive, with Norway in-between. In all three countries, national integration policy is implemented mainly at the municipal level.

Søholta, Stenbackab and Nørgaard (2018) mention earlier study of immigrants in a Norwegian rural locality (Søholt et al., 2012) that finds social esteem as a main factor that attract immigrants to stay. On the other side, social exclusion moves focus away from the individual and individuals' lack of resources and stresses 'the processes, that cause exclusion, the importance of the local context and relational issues.'

- In his assessment study of the Swedish integration debate, Andreas Johansson Heinö (2011) investigates how effective is the Swedish immigration policy. Heinö (2011) compares Sweden with other countries that faced similar integration problems. According to Heinö (2011) migrant integration has become the most urgent political issue in Sweden since 2011. Two dramatic events at the end of 2010 stand behind such awakening, the suicide bombing in the of downtown Stockholm in December 2010 and the entry of the Sweden Democrats party (SD) into the Swedish Parliament (Heinö, 2011). Sweden Democrats, the self-proclaimed nationalist, social conservative, and anti-immigration party was voted into the Swedish parliament with 5.7 percent of the vote (Towns, Karlsson, and Eyre, 2014).

Heinö (2011) focuses on definition of the concept integration and draws a distinction between it and other concepts that are relevant in this context, such as equality and identity. Furthermore, Heinö (2011) tries to illuminate the immigration debate in Sweden by examining how the concept of integration is used. Heinö (2011) contrasts integration with assimilation, equality and identity and argues that in practice integration often means assimilation. Although the term "assimilation" carries a heavy normative load, an assimilation ideal exists in both Swedish opinion and political debate. Heinö (2011) considers Swedish debate is less clearly structured than the debates in comparable countries such as Germany and Great Britain, where integration is presented as an alternative to multiculturalism, or in France and the US, where the ideal is still expressed in terms of assimilation. According to Heinö (2011) the Swedish integration debate is dominated by an ideal of equality at the expense of an ideal of freedom. The various fates of Swedes and immigrants are interpreted as both problems of integration and equality,

which make it difficult to distinguish between integration and equality. Heinö (2011) sees that this is quite normal from a leftist ideological perspective, where Swedish center-right politicians tend to prioritize (language requirements, burqa bans, social contracts) instead of adopting a liberal integration policy that prioritizes the individual and civil society. Heinö (2011) concludes that it is difficult to separate integration from identity:

'In practice "Swedish" and integrated converge: a person who is integrated is Swedish and a person who is not Swedish is not integrated. Meanwhile Swedish identity is often highlighted as an obstacle to integration.' (Heinö, 2011)

- In a research that studies obligatory integration, migrants need to acquire language skills, knowledge of the history and culture of the host society and 'norm adherence' to be granted permanent residency or citizenship. The concept of mandatory integration promotes the civic skills of migrants to enable them to be integrated politically, socially, and economically. In their study, Goodman and Wright (2015) examine whether civic integration is a proper solution to fix integration problems. To study civic integration policy, Goodman and Wright (2015) use data from six waves of the European Social Survey (2002–2012). They find that several Western European countries have adopted mandatory integration in their integration policies, whereas Sweden so far has not required any level of the Swedish language to grant immigrants Swedish citizenship, however, Goodman and Wright (2015) find proofs that obligatory integration requirement produces a long-term, tangible integration change in Western European countries (Goodman and Wright, 2015).

2.1.2 Integration literature – immigrants

More research study integration at immigrants' side and less from immigrants' perspective. These studies investigate how immigrant socio-economic integration can be affected by neighborhoods (Wimark, Haandrikman and Nielsen, 2019), the type of granted residency permit (Jutvik and Robinson, 2018) or by waiting time that refugees spend before they get the residence permit in the host society (Bakker, Dagevos, and Engbersen, 2014).

- In the socio-economic integration context, some studies have found that residence in deprived neighborhoods prevents immigrants' employment. Wimark, Haandrikman and Nielsen (2019) analyses some of neighborhood characteristics, such as level of deprivation and they find that residence in immigrant-dense and deprived neighborhoods negatively affects immigrants' employment, income situation and their education level. Wimark, Haandrikman and Nielsen (2019) examine the association between the initial settlement and immigrants' employment

and income. Unlike previous studies that mostly used administratively defined geographical units, which may ignore neighborhood effects, Wimark, Haandrikman and Nielsen (2019) uses individualized neighborhoods where they are constructed based on each individual's nearest neighbors using geocoded register data, on different scales and follow three groups of migrants and examines the relationship between the initial neighborhoods that migrants settle in and their employment and income, in the short and medium-long term. According to Wimark, Haandrikman and Nielsen (2019), the results show obvious associations between neighborhoods of initial settlement and labour market integration. Immigrants who start off in neighborhoods with high levels of deprivation is associated with lower levels of employment while settling in rich neighborhoods is associated with higher incomes (Wimark, Haandrikman and Nielsen, 2019).

- In the labour market integration context, Jutvik and Robinson (2018) study the effects of permanent residency on labour market participation in Sweden. They make use of the sudden policy change implemented in Sweden in 2013, when the Swedish Migration Agency re-assessed the conflict in Syria and consequently, consequently, Syrian asylum seekers were granted permanent instead of temporary residency. Jutvik and Robinson (2018) highlight Rights-based and Responsibilities-based model of integration. The Rights-based model of integration claims that permanent and secure residency leads to effective inclusion in the host society. On the other side, the Responsibility-based model advocates the notion that to facilitate migrants' inclusion into the host society, they must be granted temporary residence permit, if they meet specific criteria such as full-time job then they can be eligible for permanent residency. Responsibilities-based models argue that migrants need to make more effort to be integrated (Jutvik and Robinson, 2018). Using detailed Swedish registry data, Jutvik and Robinson (2018) examine the effect of the permanent residency on migrant labour market inclusion in Sweden. Findings of Jutvik and Robinson (2018) study are twofold, firstly, they conclude that immigrants with temporary residents who are subject to a relatively less-inclusive situation earn more and are less unemployed than immigrants with permanent residency. Secondly, immigrants with temporary residents are less likely to spend time in education than are those with permanent residency

- Bakker, Dagevos, and Engbersen (2014) study the impact of waiting time that refugees spend to get residence permit on their socio-economic integration (Bakker, Dagevos, and Engbersen, 2014). The study uses detailed information on about 4,000 refugees to show that also post-migration stressors affect mental health and hinder the socio-economic integration of the four

largest refugee groups in the Netherlands: Afghan, Iraqi, Iranian and Somali. According to Bakker, Dagevos, and Engbersen (2014), lack of resources and uncertainty about the future that refugees experience during the waiting period impact their ability to integrate with the host society. In addition to pre-migration stressors, Bakker, Dagevos, and Engbersen (2014) highlight the impact of 'post-migration stressors' on the mental health of the refugees that affect their socio-economic integration in the host society later.

2.2 Research Gap and Study Contribution

Despite the valuable insights of available integration research, it is noticeable that the voice of immigrants is absent in most of them. The existing researches that study non-European immigrant integration focus on integration from the host society perspective and even when they address challenges that migrants face in the host society, the perspective of the host community is most present in addressing such challenges. There are less studies that consider both perspectives (host and migrant) in one study. This study attempts to add the views of non-European immigrants on integration issues raised in some previous research and presents both perspectives of Swedes and non-European immigrants on the interrelationship between interactive integration and labor market integration. While Søholta, Stenbackab and Nørgaard (2018) examine immigrants' roles in co-producing local resilience, this study combines immigrants and Swedes' perspective about mechanisms that make immigrants' roles more effective in co-producing local resilience through the one of the four dimensions of social integration, the structural integration (migrant access to labour market).

Heinö (2011) highlights the definition of the concept integration and draws a distinction between it and other concepts that are relevant in this context, as equality and identity, this study aims to investigate how do both non-European immigrants and Swedes perceive the concept of 'integration' and being 'Swedish' through identification integration. Using interactive and cultural integration, this study puts both perspectives (host and migrant) about obstacles that prevent their social interaction integration, while Wimark, Haandrikman and Nielsen (2019) analyses the level of deprivation as one of neighborhood characteristics, and how it negatively affects immigrants' employment and income situation.'

Moreover, this study highlights the correlation between the migrants' integration in the Swedish labor market, which facilitates their social interaction with the host society, from one side, and their social interaction, which provides them with personal contacts that facilitate their access to the Swedish labor market on the other side.

3. Theoretical Framework

To answer the research question, this study uses Bosswick and Heckmann's (2006) four dimension of social integration as a theoretical framework. Throughout this paper, Bosswick and Heckmann's framework be used as a guideline to know how non-European immigrants and Swedes perceive the challenges and opportunities of non-European immigrants' social integration into the Swedish society.

3.1. Bosswick and Heckmann's (2006) four dimension of social integration

Social integration is one aspect of immigrant integration in a host society. It gives immigrant knowledge about the socialization process under certain conditions (Bosswick and Heckmann, 2006, pp-9). Social integration allow immigrant to acquire a social status, and to learn about culture in host society, to build personal contacts and relationships with the native residents and to grow a feeling of belonging to the society (ibid, 2006, pp-11). Immigrants face different difficulties on arrival at a new country. They lack language skills, economic security, and certainty of their staying length. They cannot access certain places of in the host society, such as voting or political activities (ibid, 2006, pp-33). According to Bosswick and Heckmann, there are four dimensions of social integration: structural, cultural, interactive and identification integration.

3.1.1. Structural integration

Structural integration means the incorporation of immigrant into the main institutions of the host society such as the educational system and the labor market. To access the core institutions in the host society and get its position, immigrants need cultural competencies. The structural integration is a process that takes place broadly at the urban level. This kind of integration is into national society, particularly in local and regional context (Bosswick and Heckmann 2006, pp-9). The economic institutions are essential system in the host society. The educational system seen as the door of the economic institutions. Both institutions (economic and educational) help to get socioeconomic position. Individual in society must gain required cognitive, cultural, and social competence to get a position in society and play a role in its socioeconomic institutions and systems (ibid, 2006. pp-9).

3.1.2. Cultural integration

Cultural integration means that immigrants must obtain required knowledge and competencies about culture and society to claim rights and undertake positions in the host society. (Bosswick

and Heckmann 2006, pp-10). Cultural integration primarily seen as a responsibility of immigrants; however, it can be a two-way process. It can be from the host society also. Migration changes the host society; residents need to learn about immigrants and adapting to their needs. Cultural integration does not mean that immigrants have to give up their own culture of their homelands. Bicultural competencies and personalities are an asset both for the individual and the host society (ibid, 2006, pp-10).

3.1.3. Interactive Integration

Interactive integration refers to relationships and the social networks of immigrants in society. According to Bosswick and Heckmann (2006), the communicative competencies are preconditions for interactive integration. Immigrant needs to learn the language of the host society and use it to communicate with the people. Immigrants start this interactive integration with former immigrants. Immigrants' interactive integration into social systems of the 'ethnic colony' in the host society may help them as a first step of the integration process through sharing of information and experiences. On the other side, such integration may prevent immigrants from creating contact with the host society and acquiring required cultural and social capital that enable them to compete in the core institutions of the host society (Bosswick and Heckmann 2006, pp-10).

3.1.4. Identification Integration

According to Bosswick and Heckmann (2006), A society is not homogenous: it is stratified vertically and has marginalized subcultures, in which immigrants may be integrated. (Bosswick and Heckmann,2006, pp-11). Bosswick and Heckmann (2006) argue that immigrants cannot participate in a host society's core institutions without acquiring the cultural competencies by which these institutions function. (ibid, 2006, pp-10). Identification integration means that immigrant feels a real sense of belonging in the new society. Without such sense of belonging immigrant cannot participate in institutions in the host society. The feeling of belonging can improve the integration process and increase immigrant's acceptance and participation in the host society. Inclusion in a new society refers the identification integration. It indicates the feelings of belonging to, and identification with, groups, particularly in ethnic, regional, local and national identification (ibid, 2006, pp-10).

4. Methodology

In this part, the research design and method selection are described in detail. It contains six sections: research design, interview guide, research setting, research participants, ethics and limitations.

4.1. Research Design

This is an explorative study that guided by Bosswick and Heckmann's (2006) four-fold theory of social integration. This type of research aims to get understanding of an existing problem; however, it does not provide conclusive results. This study starts from a general idea about non-European immigrant integration in Sweden as the main issue, explorative method helps to understand the perceptions of both Swedes and non-European immigrants about the obstacles that prevent immigrants from integrating into the host society.

This study uses interview as a 'the most appropriate research technique to operationalize the theoretical framework'. The exploratory qualitative interviews help researcher to get better understanding of 'distinctive features of situations and events and the beliefs of individuals or sub-cultures'. Studying immigrant integration problem from the two different perspectives (immigrants and Swedes) requires explicating things that have been implicit to articulate their perceptions, feelings and understanding'' (Arksey and Knight, 1999). Interviews help researcher to get information from respondents or to get their own ideas and perceptions about the issue. This study focuses mostly on interviewees perceptions, thereby treating the interview subjects as respondents. The list of respondents includes 25 respondents. 11 non-European immigrants who moved to Sweden during the last decade, 5 former non-European immigrants who moved to Sweden during 1980s, 1990s and 2000s (Appendix B1). 9 Swedes who live in different areas (Appendix B2).

This study tries to interview as many as possible and feasible, since it aims to get as many as varied and multi-versed experiences, perspectives, and views from the interviewees, so it can reach its exploratory ambition.

The interview guides (Appendix A1 & A2) have been generated from the theoretical framework of the four dimensions of social integration by Bosswick and Heckmann. In the current study, the theoretical framework is used to understand the empirical evidence generated not for theory-testing. It focuses on how Swedes and non-European immigrants perceive the challenges that face them in the host society. In both interview guides, questions are formulated

to be related to each of the theoretical dimensions. The author has chosen to collect the data from the respondents using semi-structured interviews. After conducting the semi structured interview, they were carefully "scripted". Questions formulated in four groups, basic information, identification integration, labor market integration and social integration. They be asked sequence, sometimes without follow-up (Marshall and Rossman, 2016). It is crucial in the semi-structured interview to allows interviewers to find out how research participants view their social world and that there is flexibility in the conduct of the interviews (Alan Bryman,2012 pp- 473). Most interviews were conducted via Zoom because of the current Covid-19 pandemic.

4.2 Interview Guide

Before conducting the interviews, the author created two interview guides based on the four dimensions of social integration theory of Bosswick and Heckmann (2006). One interview guide for non-European immigrants attached in Appendix A1 (See Appendix A1 on page 41). Another interview guide is designed for Swedes attached in Appendix A2 (See Appendix A2 on page 44)

Interview Guide (Non-European Immigrants)

The first part of non-European immigrants' interview guide focuses on Age, Gender, living in city or countryside, professions, education, family (How many people, including the interviewee, live in its household), the country of origin, year of arrival in Sweden, the reason of moving to Sweden (Refugee, family reunification/ love, student visa or work visa), Swedish citizenship, and the how interviewee evaluate its own skills in Swedish language. the Second part focuses on Identification that refers to an individual's identification with a social system where the interviewee sees himself/herself as a part of a collective body. Identification has both cognitive and emotional aspects (Heckmann, & Bosswick, 2006). Interviewees are asked about detention of 'being Swedish' and ' integration' and how they are connected to the Swedish society. The third part focuses on non-European immigrants' integration into the Swedish Labor market, to know how the interviewee perceive the obstacles that prevent him/her from integrating into the Swedish labor market and how he/she is economically integrated. The questions try to capture satisfaction with employment situation, and the ability to meet different levels of unexpected expenses (Harder et al, 2018). The fourth part of the interview guide focuses on the non-European immigrants' social integration and their interactive integration

which means the acceptance of non-European immigrants in relationships and social networks in the Swedish society (Heckmann & Bosswick, 2006).

Interview Guide (Swedes)

The first part of Swedes' interview guide focuses on basic information such as, age, gender, living in city or countryside, professions, education, family (How many people, including the interviewee, live in its household), and if one of his/her parents is born outside Sweden. The Second part interviewees are asked about definition of '*being Swedish*' and 'integration'. The third part focuses on how interviewee's experience to work with non-European immigrants and who he/she perceive the obstacles that prevent non-European immigrants from integrating into the Swedish labor market. The fourth part focuses on social integration and their daily interactive integration with non-European immigrants.

4.3 Research Setting

The Migration and Integration policies in Sweden is often described as rights-based policy (Koopmans 2010). Sweden has traditionally been known multicultural country through opening doors for refugees (Dahlstedt & Neergaard, 2019). However, reality shows that traditional Swedish integration policies have become debatable in the last decade. Since 2011, immigration and integration issues have been at the top of the political agenda in Sweden (Heinö, 2011). In the last decade, integration has become a more urgent issue, especially, when Sweden has received a huge number of refugees in 2015, most of them come from Asia, Africa and the Middle East as a refugee. Non-European immigrants face several challenges to find their position in in the Swedish Society and labor market. Based on the above mentioned, integration issue concern both Swedes and Sweden and non-European immigrant everywhere in Sweden. This Study tries to interview people from different, country of origin, age categories, gender, profession and from different municipalities in Sweden (Appendix B1 & B2).

4.4 Research Participants

This study sets criteria to find participants who qualify for the study. For non-European immigrants they:

1. Come from Asia, Africa or the Middle East
2. Moved to Sweden as a refugee, family reunification/ love, student or with work visa.

3. Have an intention to stay permanently in Sweden.
4. Have stayed in Sweden for a minimum of two years.

For Swedish respondents they:

- 1- Born and raised in Sweden
- 2- One or both her/his parents born and raised in Sweden

The table of the respondent's profile is attached in Appendix B1 & B2 (Pages 46 & 48).

4.5. Sample selection:

To select participants for each group in the study, the author uses two types, purposive and snowball sampling. The target number of participants is 25, so the author needs to have at least 50 potential participants to start the selection process. In purposive sampling, the researcher aims to find relevant participants to the posed research question. In the Study, each group members have a specific characteristic that fits with the research question, so the first selection of participants was based on a non-random basis (Bryman, 2017:408). This study uses snowball sampling also, in which some of the participants may suggest other participants with relevant characteristic to my research question (Bryman, 2017:415). The study targets two groups. The general characteristics of all participants are age (20-66), 50% women, 50% men. They live in different places in Sweden (Big cities or countryside). Variety education levels: Pre-secondary, secondary and post-secondary education.

4.6 Ethics

Bryman (2012) highlights four ethical principles: Harm to participants, lack of informed consent, invasion of privacy and deception (Alan Bryman, 2012, pp-135). In different stages of social research ethical issues may arise. This study takes Bryman's four principles into consideration during conducting potential interviews. The author got respondents' consent to record the conversations and the author started the interview with an explanation of research purpose and how their interview will be used in the study. They were informed about the nature and potential consequences of the study. Additionally, the study took relational ethics into consideration which involve an ethical 'self-consciousness' in which researcher is mindful of its character, actions, and consequences on others (Sarah J. Tracy 2010, p-847). Relational ethics are linked to an ethic of care that "recognizes and values mutual respect, dignity, and connectedness between researcher and researched, and between researchers and the

communities in which they live and work' (Sarah J. Tracy 2010, p-846). To maintain confidentiality of the research, the names of respondents are not disclosed in the transcription. The author also offered respondents the options to decline the interview altogether, which two contacts did, and to opt-out of answering. The author tried to contact a Swede who is Sweden Democrats (SD) voter through a mutual friend. He asked to read the interview guide first, the author sent him a summary of it. But he apologized for participating in the interview.

4.7 Limitations

This study uses qualitative research to get a deeper understanding of what individuals are socially constructed by their interaction with their world (Sharan B. Merriam, 2002, pp 3). The study aims to know more about Swedes and non-European immigrants' experience with identification integration in addition to labor market integration and interactive integration. This kind of qualitative research can be criticized because it is impressionistic and subjective (Alan Bryman, 2012, pp-405). Impressionistic and subjective means that such research depends much on the researcher's often unsystematic views about what is significant and essential. It also relies on the close personal relationships between researcher and the studied people.

Another limitation of this study is the number of respondents, such study needs more participants to cover more of Swedes and non-European immigrants from different backgrounds and from different places in Sweden but including more participants would require more time and resources. The final limitation is about asking Swedes about their political direction which is not accepted in Sweden. The political direction can affect their attitude towards immigrant integration. Given all of this the reader can surmise that the study should not be considered to be representative of all Swedes and migrants in Sweden, but it does offer some important insights and original empirical data on the two-way process of integration.

5. Results and Analysis

Addressing the aim of the current research to empirically explore an analytical framework that defines aspects of social integration processes, research question is set down:

How do non-European immigrants and Swedes perceive the challenges and opportunities of non-European immigrants' integration into the Swedish labour market and society?

To answer the research question and the three sub-questions, interviews are structured on the Bosswick and Heckmann's (2006) four dimensions of social integration: Identification,

Structural, Interactive, and Cultural integration. Interview guide is designed in three main sections:

- (1) Social Identification: Using Identification Integration dimension which means immigrant's feeling of belonging in the new society.
- (2) Immigrant Integration into the Swedish labour market: According to Structural Integration dimension. Structural Integration includes entering core institutions of the host society, such as the labor market or the educational system.
- (3) Social integration: this section adapts two dimensions of social integration: interactive and cultural integration. (A) Interactive Integration that includes communication, relationships, and the social networks of immigrants in society, and (B) Cultural Integration, which includes the knowledge and competencies about culture and society.

5.1.1 Identification Integration

Immigrant's feeling of belonging may grow later in the integration process because of participation and acceptance in the host society. Identification integration is specified by feelings of belonging to, and identification with, groups, particularly in ethnic, regional, local and/or national identification (Bosswick and Heckmann 2006, pp 11).

In this part, all interviewees are asked about their definition of '*being Swedish*' and of '*integration*' or how would they describe an immigrant that is *integrated* in the Swedish Society. Additional questions asked only to non-European immigrants:

- To what extent do you personally feel that you are Swedish?
- How connected do you feel with the Swedish society?
- How often do you feel like an outsider in Sweden?
- Have you experienced the feeling that you do not belong neither to the Swedish society nor to your country of origin?

5.1.2 Integration into the labor market

According to Bosswick and Heckmann (2006), entering the labor market is the first essential key for integration in the society. This part about structural integration that includes entering core institutions of the host society, such as the labor market or the educational system. The study focuses only on immigrant integration into the Swedish labour market. Majority of interviewees emphasized the importance of immigrant integration into the labor market. All respondents are asked a general question about migration impact on Swedish economic growth.

Although, few of them mentioned the burden of migration on economy, majority stressed the positive impact of migration on Swedish economic growth. However, when they are asked if the Swedish labor Market open for non-European immigrants, majority of interviewees claimed that it is open for a few segments of non-European immigrants.

5.1.3 Social integration:

Social Integration is a process that helps immigrants and the native people in the host society to live together. According to Bosswick and Heckmann (2006), this process helps immigrants to establish themselves in a new society. Social integration is a process in which immigrant access to positions and social status, learn a new culture, and acquire rights and obligations, social integration enables immigrants to build personal contacts with natives in the host society and grow feeling of belonging to the host society (Bosswick and Heckmann, 2006, pp11). In this section social integration is studied through two dimensions of social integration:

- Interactive Integration.
- Cultural Integration.

5.1.3.1 Interactive Integration.

Interactive integration includes communication, relationships, friendships, partnerships, marriages, social networks and membership in voluntary organizations immigrants in society. In this part, all interviewees are asked about their friends from other side, how often do they communicate with them, and in which activities or events they do. They asked also about obstacles that are hindering social interaction between Swedes and non-European immigrants. They asked how former non-European immigrants can impact newly arrived non-European immigrant social integration in the Swedish society.

All participants were reminded that this study does not consider the COVID-19 epidemic and the current restrictions and quarantines

5.1.3.2 Cultural integration,

Cultural integration includes knowledge and competencies about culture and society. In this part, Swedes are asked if they join non-European immigrants' celebrations. Non-European immigrants are asked if they celebrate the Swedish holidays. They are asked also if they attended Civic Orientation course (*Samhällsorientering*) ⁽⁷⁾. The course is offered to people who have recently been granted a residence permit in Sweden to learn about Swedish society

(7) Civic Orientation course (*Samhällsorientering*). A course is offered by the municipality where immigrants live with their native language. The course includes sections on: Human rights, Fundamental democratic values, Rights and obligations, How Swedish society is organized and Practical everyday life

The course is offered to people who have recently been granted a residence permit in Sweden to learn about Swedish society. Both Swedes and Non-European immigrants are asked if non-European immigrants can get integrated into the Swedish society without giving up all their own culture.

In the next section, the author presents the responses of both Swedes and non-European immigrants about identification integration, labor market integration and social integration.

5.2 Swedes' perspective

5.2.1 Identification Integration from Swede's perspective

Majority of the Swedish respondents define the term *being Swedish* as sharing history, culture, values, building welfare system, being open and tolerant and showing solidarity.

Respondent SF-34 does not identify herself as a typical Swede, she may use this definition when she travels abroad, however, she mentioned positive part of growing up in Sweden. She is proud of the country with long history of socialism (Interviewee SF-34, Gothenburg, Female).

Respondent SE-38 mentioned societal rules, which are applicable for all. She linked the term being Swedish to the welfare system, however, she highlighted that *being Swedish* is being positive and talkative during summertime; then getting quite reserved in wintertime (Interviewee SE-38, Stockholm, Female) ⁽⁶⁾.

Being Swedish for respondent SC-50 is a privilege of growing up in a safe society and having passport that allow her to normally move all around the world (Interviewee SC-50, Malmö, Female). Majority of Swedes mentioned job and speaking understandable Swedish as indicators of immigrant integration. Further, they highlighted understanding of the Swedish culture and sharing same values as a signal about immigrant integration. Few swedes define integration as immigrant responsibility. According to SA-65, immigrant must be positive and work to create a platform (job, study, language) that give him/her satisfaction in the host society. Immigrant cannot see host society as an '*enemy*', otherwise he/she may choose another country (Interviewee SA-65, Lerum, Male).

On the other side, some swedes focus on the host society responsibility in immigrant integration process. Respondent SE-38 sees that job is the only way to get in contact with the society, she

does not agree that you need to speak perfect Swedish to get job. She described integrated immigrant as a one who is invited by native swedes into their life, however, she believes this is very tricky because *'we are really not doing a good job there, I must admit.'* (Interviewee SE-38, Stockholm, Female).

Other respondents defined integration as adaptation process. Respondent SH-27 believe that integration means:

'that person will need to adapt the existing group of people's both rules and values etc. That is for me integration.' (Interviewee SH-27, Gothenburg, Male).

5.2.2 Labor Market integration from Swede's perspective

According to respondent SA-65, the labor market is difficult in Sweden, even for people born in Sweden:

'In some areas or some fields, it's difficult to have a job. For example, an architect, a biologist... It's hard work to get a job. I think the first thing is to learn the language. In a lot of jobs, you are not coming for an interview if your Swedish is not good enough.' (Interviewee SA-65, Lerum, Male).

Respondent SC-50 thinks that the Swedish labor market is not open even for European immigrants. They face challenges to find a job relevant to their educational level. She attributes that to characteristics of Scandinavian labor market, which is unique, specialized, and decentralized (Interviewee SC-50, Malmö, Female).

Respondent SG-27 thinks that non-European immigrants face challenges with their education validation. According to Respondent SG-27, it could be easier if immigrant comes from the USA to get into the Swedish labor market, because the US universities have high reputation in Sweden (Interviewee SG-27, Gothenburg, Male).

All interviewees are asked about obstacles that prevent non-European immigrants from integrating into the Swedish labor market. The answers varied between the language barrier, education, an understanding of work culture in Sweden, prejudice in the labor market and the failure of The Swedish Public Employment Service AF (*Arbetsförmedlingen*) to facilitate immigrants' entry into the Swedish labor market.

Respondent SD-39 sheds a light on how understanding labor market codes and mastering Swedish language can be obstacles for non-European immigrant even if he or she has high education and relevant work experience. He gives an example of an engineer from Syria who got internship at RISE (Research Institutes of Sweden AB) but he could not get job after the internship:

'He was the head of the water utility company there (in Damascus). He was 50-55, super experienced, super high-level boss of the utility company. And he was getting an internship in water project at RISE. He has tons of experience of the stuff he was working with, but he did not know the codes and how to like do work at this company. He had a remarkably high position in Syria. That was not, he was not able to get a similarly high-level position in Sweden, of course. So, I think that is a challenge. I mean he would need to do to write applications for reach search funds. He needs to write a version in Swedish.' (Interviewee SD-39, Alingsås, Male).

Respondent SB-61 thinks that there are prejudices on both sides, Swedish employers, and non-European immigrant. She believes that it is so important that immigrants master the language and understand how the Swedish labor market and how the Swedish society works, additionally, she thinks that Swedish labor market needs to be less prejudice (Interviewee SB-61, Stenungsund, Female).

Regarding the role of The Swedish Public Employment Service AF, respondent SE-38 thinks that it does not put effort and time on encouraging employers in Sweden to open doors and offer immigrants internships or jobs.

'AF with nearly 10,000 employees, they should, instead of putting 90% of the time on all the candidates, they should do the other way around and put 90% of their time on giving the best possible service to the Swedish employers so that these employers are willing to open up the doors to jobs so that the immigrant are getting chosen into Swedish society.' (Interviewee SE-38, Stockholm, Female).

5.2.3 Interactive integration from Swede's perspective

Majority of the Swedish respondents have a few non-European immigrant friends, instead, they have some acquaintances and coworkers. They communicate with them in some public event like after work or in some music activities such as choir.

Respondent SF-34 has many non-European immigrant friends, they are 50% of her friends. She meets them twice a month. As an activist and musician, she and meet people in activist and music activities (Interviewee SF-34, Gothenburg, Female).

Respondent SC-50 does not have too many friends who are non-European immigrants, however, she meets some of them because she is married to an Egyptian:

'I do not have many people who are non-European immigrants, but I spend my daily life with my husband who is from Egypt. And of course, he has friends who come here. And we have common friends in Malmö and Copenhagen, that are many of them are born in Denmark, but they have families from Egypt, or Palestine, or Iran.' (Interviewee SC-50, Malmö, Female)

When Swedes are asked about what is hindering non-European immigrant social interactive integration into the Swedish society, most of them admitted that Swedes are not social enough (Interviewee SA-65, Lerum, Male). For Respondent SC-50, Swedes don't interact much with anyone, not only with non-European immigrants (Interviewee SC-50, Malmö, Female). Respondent SI-23 thinks that this is a very ingrained Swedish culture (Interviewee SI-23, Stockholm, Female).

For Respondent SG-27, it is the Swedish mentality to be individualistic (Interviewee SG-27, Gothenburg, Male).

Respondent SE-38 thinks that lack interactive integration is because of Swedes. She highlighted again that Swedes can be open and positive and chatty in summertime. Otherwise, when they are quite reserved, and very private in wintertime. She suggests that Swedes need an events and activities to meet immigrant. She mentioned some initiatives she is trying to do to create such activities and event, for example, arranging for dinner with family coming from a non-European country and then they invite you to a traditional dinner, just so you get to know each other, *'food is door opener in other cultures.'* (Interviewee SE-38, Stockholm, Female).

Swedish respondents are asked how they perceive the role of former non-European immigrants in the social and interactive integration of newly arrived non-European immigrants in Swedish society. Respondent SF-34 thinks that some of former non-European immigrants impact the

newcomers negatively. They isolated themselves and focused on their own lives, even part of them is racist against other immigrants from other culture or other countries (Interviewee SF-34, Gothenburg, Female).

Some respondents believe that the former non-European immigrants will describe Swedish society based on their personal experiences. Respondent ES-38 believes that frustrated immigrants who lived in Sweden for 15 years and were excluded from society or did not have a job would not be able to be as positive to newcomer (Interviewee SE-38, Stockholm, Female).

5.2.4 Cultural integration from Swede's perspective

When Swedish respondents are asked if they participated in non-European immigrant celebrations or any traditional events in Sweden, two of them answered that they had never participated in such celebrations. Four of them participate in celebration but very rarely. The three Swedes who celebrate more often with non-European immigrants have one of their parents is immigrant, or has immigrant partner:

I lived in a Muslim country when I was a child for a few years. We celebrated Eid and weddings etc. And then all through my life, growing up, I always had non-European friends... and my partner is a non-European immigrant, so it comes naturally. (Interviewee SF-34, Gothenburg, Female).

Respondent SH-27 celebrates non-European immigrant celebrations because his mother is Vietnamese:

Of course, half of my family is Vietnamese Chinese that I have raised with. I also celebrated something with Indian friends, there I had a good food a couple of times. (Interviewee SH-27, Gothenburg, Male).

Responding to question if non-European immigrants can get integrated into the Swedish society without giving up all their own culture, majority of Swedish respondents replied (*Yes*).

Respondent SE-38 thinks that Sweden is still multicultural, however, she expressed some concerns:

That is a dream. It must be like that. I have a colleague or a friend who said "I want to integrate with integrity. I do not take my Hijab off. I don't want to celebrate our cultural activities and not being able to talk

about them” And I completely agree. I just think it is so scary to hear some people feel like that, and if society is developing towards such a direction, then it’s completely wrong. I think we have room for all these cultural activities. (Interviewee SE-38, Stockholm, Female).

Respondent SA-65 believe that some Swedes do not want to leave their own comfort zone here in Swed, whereas they appreciate something different when they are abroad as tourists (Interviewee SA-65, Lerum, Male).

5.3 Non-European Immigrant perspective

5.3.1 Identification Integration from non-European Immigrant perspective

The 16 Non-European immigrant respondents have various perceptions about the definition of ‘*being Swedish*’. The privilege of possessing a passport that allows immigrant to move freely around the world. The sense of belonging to a society which law applies to everyone and believing in Swedish liberal social values. One respondent defines the term *being Swedish*, as being born to Swedish parents or one of them is Swedish. He does not consider himself Swedish, he just tries to do what is expected from him in the Swedish society (Interviewee MJ-40, Palestine, Male).

Four respondents understand *being Swedish* as a citizenship and passport that allow them to move freely over the world. Being Swedish to respondent ML-34, is an alternative identity since he is (stateless) (Interviewee ML-34, Palestine, Male). For respondent MO-15, to be Swedish is believing in the liberal social values (Interviewee MO-15, Somalia, Male). Respondent MP-9 sees it as being integrated in the society and doing the norms and culture like the Swedes (Interviewee MP-9, Indonesia, Female).

Respondents MR-7 highlighted the impact of the Swedish standers on her daily behavior, she mentioned the respect of privacy, planning for every work, and punctuality, however, she insists that she is 100% Tunisian (Interviewee MR-7, Tunisian, Female).

Although non-European immigrants are defined differently by the term "*being Swedish*", most of them have shown a good connection to Swedish society. Most of them emphasized that their connection to the Swedish institutions is stronger than their connection to Swedes. Responding to a question about their feeling as an outsider in Sweden, majority of non-European immigrants experienced such feeling. This feeling can be normal on arrival or when immigrant

lacks language skills to communicate with people in host society. It is worth noting that some of them still feel this way after decades in Sweden. Respondent MK-35 feel as an outsider when he comes to a new workplace, Swedish colleagues judge him as a newcomer (Interviewee MK-35, Iran, Male).

When Non-European immigrant respondents were asked about their definition of the concept of integration or their description of the immigrant who is integrated into Swedish society, majority of them mentioned Swedish language and job as measures of integration. Respondent MQ-9 highlighted volunteer work and participation in civil society activities as an alternative until immigrant finds his/her place in the Swedish labor market (Interviewee MQ-9, Sudan, Female).

Some of non-European immigrants highlighted immigrant's ability to adapt to Swedish standards and culture without giving up his or her original culture (Interviewee MV-6, Gaza Strip, Female).

5.3.2 Labor Market integration from non-European immigrant perspective

Respondent MJ-40 agreed that the Swedish labor market is not open even for swedes. He mentioned his Swedish colleague, he was a pilot and worked for two years in the Warehouse before he found job as a pilot abroad (Interviewee MJ-40, Palestine, Male).

Respondent MK-35 thinks that the Swedish labour Market is open just to certain places, not everywhere, and for certain groups of immigrants. He gives two examples: (a) many Thai and Vietnamese immigrants work in the cleaning sector. (b) Most Somali women can find a job only in at (*hemtjänst*) home care sector (Interviewee MK-35, Iran, Male).

Respondent MQ-9 is a job seeker and holds a PhD in Physics from a Swedish University. She believes that there is great injustice in the labor market for the high educated immigrants (Interviewee MQ-9, Sudan, Female).

Respondent MV-6 shed light on a fundamental difference between some professions in her country of origin and Sweden regarding required education and license:

Carpenter needs to study carpentry and get certificate that entitles him to practice the profession in Sweden, something that does not exist in my country and perhaps in most of the countries of the Middle East.

According to MV-6, non-European immigrant needs to get required education even if he or she has work experience from his original country (Interviewee MV-6, Gaza Strip, Female).

5.3.3 Interactive integration from non-European immigrant perspective

On the other hand, non-European immigrants try to have Swedish friends, but they do not always succeed. It is paradox in this study that the oldest immigrant among the respondents does not have any Swedish friends after 40 years in Sweden, while the latest newly arrived immigrant has many Swedish friends after two years in Sweden. Respondent MJ-40 claimed that he does not have Swedish friends:

Unfortunately, I have been for forty years in Sweden, and I do not have any Swedish friends, knowing that I invited some Swedes to my house, and I did not find any response, sometimes I consider it a matter of (chemistry). I wished they would invite me to a party, a wedding, or even a funeral. I never received an invitation; just want to feel I am a part of this community. Tired of initiatives with no result. (Interviewee MJ-40, Palestine, Male)

For Respondent MY-2, Swedish friends help him to find job and to learn Swedish faster. They can be a reference for him in the future. Respondent MY-2 arrived in Sweden in 2019. He claimed that 90% of his friends are Swedes, however, he mentioned that he does not communicate with them that much because he knows that most of Swedes do not like too much communication. (Interviewee MY-2, Yemen, Male)

When Non-European immigrant are asked about what is hindering their social interactive integration into the Swedish society, they mentioned several reasons. Some of respondents mention that Swedes are cautious with strangers (Interviewee MW-5, Syria, Male).

Others believe that religious beliefs of some non-European immigrants may prevent them from interacting with the host society. Respondent MU-7 thinks that some immigrants approach Swedish society through their own religion. The information and reactions they received from the Swedish society are treated from a religious point of view. This is a big problem that hinders the mutual acceptance between non-European immigrant and the host society (Interviewee MU-7, Syria, Female).

Respondent MQ-9 believes that immigrants who lack of sufficient language skills avoid interacting with the Swedes, and sometimes they fear to be exposed to a racist reaction. (Interviewee MQ-9, Sudan, Female).

Respondent MP-9 thinks that Swedes are quite closed. It is kind of normal cultural difference. For her, this not negative and immigrants need to understand it and to put effort to start (Interviewee MP-9, Indonesia, Female).

Respondents of non-European immigrants are asked how former non-European immigrants impact their social and interactive integration into the Swedish society.

Some respondents see that the former non-European immigrants will portray Swedish society according to their personal experiences. Respondent MY-2, believes that if former immigrants are integrated and successful in society, they will support newly arrived immigrants and facilitate their integration into society and vice versa. (*Interviewee MY-2, Yemen, Male*)

Respondent MX-4 sees the former non-European immigrants supportive (Interviewee MX-4, Iran, Male).

Respondent MS-7 thinks that the role of former immigrants is negative and can be frustrating:

After gaining residency in Sweden in 2014, I visited the office to register there and was excited. In the waiting time, I met a woman there who told me I would not find work in Sweden. She told me that she is a doctor who has lived in Sweden for several years without a job. It was very disappointing to me. (Interviewee MS-7, Jordan, Female)

5.3.4. Cultural integration from non-European immigrant perspective

After receiving their residence permit, non-European immigrant are offered Civic Orientation to learn about Swedish society. The course is offered in the native language of the immigrant. It is designed to provide immigrant with information about Swedish society. The course includes information about accessing Swedish institutions and practical everyday life. Only four of the 16 respondents followed this course. Two of them claimed that they have benefited from this course.

Respondent MR-7 thinks that the course focuses on laws and contained a lot of information without the presence of dialogue, discussion, or exercises. It lacks more practical things an immigrant can use in his life (Interviewee MR-7, Tunisian, Female).

Celebrating Swedish holidays can be an opportunity for non-European immigrant to meet Swedes and form contacts that enhance his integration into society. Non-European immigrants

are asked if they celebrate Swedish holidays? such as midsummer, Christmas Valborg, Fat Tuesday.

Some of respondents mentioned that they celebrate Swedish celebrations in case they are invited. Few respondents did not receive any invitation to participate in the Swedish celebrations. Half of the respondents participated in Swedish celebrations with their Swedish friends at least once. Respondents, MW-5 participates in all events. In the beginning I was invited as a guest but now after five years in Sweden I have become one of the staff organizing such celebrations.

On the other side respondent MO-15 he never celebrates Swedish holidays, for religious reason as most of Swedish celebration has alcoholic drinks. (Interviewee MO-15, Somalia, Male).

Majority of on-European immigrants think that they can get integrated into the Swedish society without giving up all their own culture. Most of them think it is a mutual respect process

Respondent MX-4 thinks that immigrant cannot be integrated in the host society without giving up something of their culture (Interviewee MX-4, Iran, Male).

Respondent MT-7 claimed that immigrants need to adapt themselves and to be in the middle (Interviewee MT-7, Afghanistan, Male).

Respondent MP-9 believe that you need to show integrity, but you also must be flexible at the same time. Should be limits on what you have to give up and what you want to keep. You have to meet Swedes somewhere in the middle (Interviewee MP-9, Indonesia, Female).

For Respondent MY-2, it is possible that non-European immigrant can integrate into the Swedish society without giving up his/her culture. He believes that Swedes accept you as you are.

They are smart and know if you are yourself or if you are pretending.

(Interviewee MY-2, Yemen, Male)

6. Analytical framework

In this section the author analyzes the interviewees' responses by presenting the similarities and differences between Swedes and non-European immigrants' perspectives on the challenges and opportunities for integrating non-European immigrants into Swedish society.

6.1 Identification Integration

Almost all respondents -non-European immigrants and Swedes- somehow mentioned the Swedish values and standards in their definition of *being Swedish*. They shed light on speaking Swedish and working as key requirement to be integrated into the Swedish Society.

As for differences, majority of Swedish respondents highlighted history, solidarity, and welfare system while talking about *being Swedish*, when majority of non-European immigrants mentioned citizenship, Swedish passport, and equality, things that could be missing in their original countries.

Some Swedish respondents defined integration as adaptation or being part of the Swedish society by fulfilling both job and language conditions. On other side, some non-European immigrants mention immigrants who can speak a fluent Swedish and a have job and still not integrated into the Swedish Society, instead, they live in segregated suburbs of the major cities in Sweden (Interviewee MK-35, Iran, Male). While defining the term '*integration*', no one of Swedish respondent mention the social aspect of integration. Further, responding to a question about their non-European immigrant, majority of Swedes mentioned that they have very few immigrant friends. On the other hand, some non-European Immigrants emphasized the social integration as the only measure immigrant integration. Respondent MJ-40 believes that if you have Swedish friend that you can communicate with him/her comfortably and spontaneously, without prior arrangements, so you are really integrated into Swedish society (Interviewee MJ-40, Palestine, Male)

6.2 Integration into the labor market

Both non-European immigrants and Swedes mentioned the Swedish language as a major obstacle that prevent non-European immigrant integration into the Swedish labor market.

Most Swedish respondents mentioned that non-European immigrants' lack of understanding work codes as an obstacle to access the Swedish labor Market.

Some Swedish respondents have been boldest in posing the problem of bias of some Swedish employers against immigrants. SE-38 is the only Swedish respondent who criticized AF role in supporting non-European immigrants to enter the labor market, because she works in the field of the labor market and has information about AF performance.

On the other hand, non-European immigrants are asked if they receive services from The Swedish Public Employment Service and how do they assess such service. Nine of the sixteen

non-European immigrant respondents are registered at AF, however, majority of them gave feedback, from their own experience or from their friends or relatives'. Respondent ML-34 received support from AF to study. Respondent MW-5 mentioned that AF helped him to get an internship. Other respondents are not satisfied with AF for various reasons; some of them believe that AF provides only information about labor market without tangible efforts to connect immigrants with Swedish employers. Some of them believe that AF works slowly, and the reason is lack of staff. Respondent MQ-9 claimed that her case officer at AF suggested that she apply for a job at nursing home or kindergarten, while she holds a PhD in physics from a Swedish university (Interviewee MQ-9, Sudan, Female).

After all respondents answered questions about the obstacles that hinder the integration of non-European immigrants into the Swedish labor market, they were asked about advice or suggestion that might help non-European immigrants to find work. As usual, the answers varied from learning the Swedish language, obtaining additional education, flexibility in changing professional competence if required, understanding how the job market works and its codes, and working on improve their presentation by working on building an attractive CV. But it is remarkable that all the Swedish respondents and non-European immigrants agreed and emphasized the importance of personal contacts in finding work in Sweden. Personal contacts need better social integration. To obtain a network of personal contacts, a non-European immigrant needs to communicate with Swedish friends, neighbors, and acquaintances, in other word, they need better social integration.

6.3 Social Integration

6.3.1 Interactive Integration

Both non-European immigrants and Swedes agree that Swedes that immigrant interactive integration into the Swedish society can be better. The majority of respondents understand the obstacles -in both sides- that prevent interactive integration between non-European immigrants and Swedes. Most Swedish respondents admitted that Swedes are not social enough. On the other side some non-European immigrant respondents highlighted how immigrant's religious beliefs can hinder their interactive communication with Swedes. Some of them mentioned the negative impact of former immigrants who portray the Swedish society from their own experience, and sometimes it could be negative and impact newly arrived immigrant social integration.

Some old immigrants show better understanding of nature of Swedish society. Respondent ML-34 believes that Swedish society is a cold society. He claims that he understands the reasons. For him, Swedish society is a working society where people do not have much time to communicate with others:

Swedes go home to rest after the workday. Historically the Swedish society was described as an agricultural community. Additionally, cold weather and distances affect the nature of people. Now 50% of Swedes live alone. After three decades in Sweden, I became like them. (Interviewee ML-34, Palestine, Male).

Differences emerge when each side suggest solutions to improve immigrant interactive integration. Some Swedes find it difficult to change society, they think it is easier if non-European immigrants try to adapt themselves to Swedish society. On the other hand, not all immigrants are ready for such adaptation process as long as they can easily find place with segregated ethnic group somewhere in Sweden.

Respondent SB-61 advises immigrants to knock the doors and try to show up in the society. On the other hand, respondent MJ-40 claimed that he tried many times to knock the door without positive response of his Swedish acquaintances. Respondent SD-39 believes that Swedes do not hangout without reason. He suggests that immigrants join some clubs to create friendships that may lead to better interaction with Swedes (Interviewee SD-39, Alingsås, Male).

Respondent MJ-40 believes that removing barriers between immigrants and Swedes requires initiative of the stronger party. For him, Swedes are the stronger party (Interviewee MJ-40, Palestine, Male)

6.3.2 Cultural Integration

The interviews try to explore non-European immigrant interactive integration with Swedes by asking all interviewees about their participation in the other's holidays and events. The majority of respondents believe that Sweden is still multicultural and non-European immigrants can integrate into Swedish society without giving up their culture, however, there are some respondents who believe that immigrants need to give up part of their culture in order to integrate. It is a process of adaptation to society. In most of the respondents' answers in this research, a question is upraised about the role of each party in integration process. According to The European Integration policy definition, integration is “a dynamic, two-way process of

mutual accommodation by all immigrants and residents of member states". All respondents are asked how does this two-way process work in Sweden. Majority of respondents see it two-way process in theory, in practice it is not. Respondents Mk-35, MO-15, MT-7, MN-19, MJ-40, SA-65, SH-27, and SC-50 see it two-way process in theory, in practice it is not.

Respondents Mk-35 thinks that Swedish people do not integrate themselves to immigrant.

this is something which they know themselves, that they don't do. And this is something open. They say all the time when everywhere. On media, when you go to Arbetsförmedlingen and when you go to school, they tell you: you are immigrant here and you have to integrate yourself to this country. But I have not seen some Swedish people integrate, I am working in the school many years. I see teachers, they are teaching, Swedish language to immigrant, maybe 20 years, but they don't know one single word in Arabic or Persian. So, they do not know the tradition of these people, who they are teaching to. So no, I think it's just one way. They expect all the time that immigrants should integrate themselves to the society (Interviewee MK-35, Iran, Male).

On the other side, respondent MW-5 sees it two-way process. He believes that there is a welcome from Swedes. But the immigrant must take the initiative:

'Because I came to this country, and I must take the initiative.'
(Interviewee MW-5, Syria, Male).

7. Discussion

The interviews showed that the respondents perceive non-European immigrant integration into Sweden in various ways according to different theoretical dimensions of social integration. There are some variations in the identification dimension between non-European immigrant and Swedish respondents regarding feeling of belonging. All respondents consider Swedish values and standards in their definition of being Swedish, however, history, solidarity, and welfare system are mentioned by Swedes when non-European immigrants consider citizenship, Swedish passport, and equality in their definition of being Swedish. Majority of Swedish respondents highlighted job and Swedish language in defining integrated immigrant, where no one mentioned social dimension in their definition. Some non-European immigrant respondent emphasized the social aspect in the same definition.

In the structural dimension, both non-European immigrants and Swedish respondents agreed that the Swedish language is a major obstacle that prevent non-European immigrant integration into the Swedish labour market. Swedish respondents highlighted kind of prejudice in the Swedish labour Market. Most respondents showed their dissatisfaction with The Swedish Public Employment Service role in matching non-European immigrant job seekers with Swedish employers. All respondents emphasized the significance of personal contacts for non-European immigrant to inter the labour market. They cannot obtain such personal contacts without interactive integration into the Swedish Society.

As for interactive dimension, majority of Swedish respondents admitted that Swedes are not social enough. Some respondents highlighted the negative impact of former immigrants who portray the Swedish society from their own experience, and sometimes it could be negative and impact newly arrived immigrant social integration. Some Swedish respondents suggested that non-European immigrants join a club and choir to make Swedish friend. Swedes prefer to meet people in events and activities. When it comes to cultural dimension, many non-European immigrant respondents celebrate Swedish Holidays, and traditions or at least they want to do if they are invited. On the other side a few of Swedes celebrate immigrant celebrations in Sweden. Many respondents believe that Sweden is still multicultural, and immigrants can integrate into Swedish society without giving up their culture, however, there are some respondents who believe that immigrants need to give up part of their culture to be integrated in the host society. It is a give-and-take process.

Majority of respondents see integration in Sweden as a two-way process in theory, but in practice it is not. Some respondents believe that immigrant integration is two-way process with the Swedish Government and institutions. Some Non-European immigrant respondents believe that immigrant integration with Swedes it is one way process, from immigrant side.

8. Conclusion

This thesis aims to explore how non-European immigrants and Swedes perceive concept of integration as a two-way process in various ways according to the four theoretical dimensions of social integration. This study claims that voice of immigrants is absent in most of available integration research despite the valuable insights they provide. The study tries to make the voice of non-European immigrants heard in the integration debate in Sweden. It combines non-European immigrants and Swedes' perspective about mechanisms that make immigrants' roles more effective in co-producing local resilience. This study puts both perspectives (host

and migrant) about obstacles that prevent their social interaction integration, Finally, it highlights the correlation between the migrant integration in the Swedish labor market and their social interaction with the Swedish society. Twenty-fivesemi-structured interviews were conducted in this thesis with sixteen non-European immigrants and nine Swedes in Sweden. Bosswick and Heckmann's four dimensions of social integration theory is used a theoretical framework.

To conclude, the interviews showed that the respondents perceive non-European immigrant integration into the Swedish society and labor market in different ways. Majority of respondents highlighted the significance of personal contacts to get job in Sweden. Non-European immigrants need to have better interactive integration with Swedes to have personal contacts that increase their chances in the Swedish labour market. Majority of respondents consider non-European immigrant integration in the Swedish society as a two-way process in theory, but in practice, some respondents believe that immigrant integration is two-way process with the 'Swedish institutions. As for the integration with Swedes, it is one way process.

Finally, if this thesis is allowed to present policy recommendation, it will emphasize the role of Swedish institutions in facilitating integration process of. Swedish institutions can do more effort to let Swedes and non-European immigrants know more about each other which make integration two-way process. Institutions can do this by creating more occasions for such meetings and by supporting civil society organizations that make the two-way process possible. It is unreasonable to ask all immigrants to initiate and knock doors, just as it is not possible to ask Swedes to open the doors.

9. References List

Anthias, F., Morokvasic-Müller, M., & Kontos, M. (2013). *Introduction: Paradoxes of integration*. In *Paradoxes of Integration: Female Migrants in Europe* (pp. 1-16). Springer, Dordrecht.

Arksey, H., & Knight, P. T. (1999). *Interviewing for social scientists: An introductory resource with examples*. Sage.

Bakker, L., Dagevos, J., & Engbersen, G. (2014). The importance of resources and security in the socio-economic integration of refugees. A study on the impact of length of stay in asylum accommodation and residence status on socio-economic integration for the four largest refugee groups in the Netherlands. *Journal of International Migration and Integration*, 15(3), 431-448..

Bryman, Alan (2012) *Social Research Methods*. Oxford. 4th Edition. Oxford University Press. PP- 379- 683).

Bryman, A., 2017. *Social Research Methods - 5th Edition*. OXFORD, Oxford University Press.

Dahlstedt, M., & Neergaard, A. (2019). Crisis of Solidarity? Changing Welfare and Migration Regimes in Sweden. *Critical Sociology*, 45(1), 121–135. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0896920516675204>

D'Haenens, L., Joris, W., & Heinderyckx, F. (2019). *Images of Non-European immigrants and Refugees in Western Europe*. Leuven University Press.

European Integration and Migration Policy, 2014

Goodman, S. W., & Wright, M. (2015). Does mandatory integration matter? Effects of civic requirements on immigrant socio-economic and political outcomes. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 41(12), 1885-1908. <https://www.slideserve.com/liona/a-common-european-integration-policy-in-sweden>

Heckmann, F., & Bosswick, W. (2006). Integration of migrants: Contribution of local and regional authorities. <http://eurofound.europa.eu/pubdocs/2006/22/en/1>.

Johansson Heinö, A. (2011). *Integration or Assimilation? An Assessment of the Swedish Integration Debate*.

Jutvik, K., & Robinson, D. (2018). Limited time or secure residence? A study on the short-term effects of temporary and permanent residence permits on labour market participation

Koopmans, R. (2010). Trade-offs between equality and difference: Immigrant integration, multiculturalism and the welfare state in cross-national perspective. *Journal of ethnic and migration studies*, 36(1), 1-26.

Marshall, Catherine & Rossman, Gretchen B. (2016) *Designing Qualitative Research* (6th ed.). Los Angeles: Sage Publications (350 pp.).

Merriam, S. B. (2002). Introduction to qualitative research. *Qualitative research in practice: Examples for discussion and analysis*, 1(1), 1-17.

MIPEX, (2020) <https://www.mipex.eu/what-is-mipex>

Moa Bursell (2012) Name change and destigmatization among Middle Eastern non-European immigrants in Sweden, *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 35:3, 471-487, DOI: 10.1080/01419870.2011.589522

OECD (2016a). *The labour market integration of immigrants and their children in Sweden*. Paris: OECD Publishing.

Petersson, S. (2014). *Utrikes födda på arbetsmarknaden: En forskningsöversikt*, Stockholms Universitets Linnécentrum för Integrationsstudier.

Statistics Sweden SCB, (2019) <https://www.scb.se/en/finding-statistics/statistics-by-subject-area/labour-market/labour-force-surveys/labour-force-surveys-lfs/pong/statistical-news/labour-force-surveys-lfs-labour-force-surveys-lfs-annual-averages-2019/>

Søholt, S., Stenbacka, S., & Nørgaard, H. (2018). Conditioned receptiveness: Nordic rural elite perceptions of immigrant contributions to local resilience. *Journal of rural studies*, 64, 220-229.

Søholt, S., Aasland, A., Onsager, K., & Vestby, G. M. (2012). "Derfor blir vi her"-innvandrere i Distrikts-Norge.

Towns, A., Karlsson, E., & Eyre, J. (2014). The equality conundrum: Gender and nation in the ideology of the Sweden Democrats. *Party Politics*, 20(2), 237–247. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354068813520272>

Tracy, Sarah J (2010) "Qualitative Quality: Eight 'Big-Tent' Criteria for Excellent Qualitative Research." *Qualitative Inquiry*, 16(10), 837-851.

Wimark, T., Haandrikman, K., & Nielsen, M. M. (2019). Migrant labour market integration: The association between initial settlement and subsequent employment and income among migrants. *Geografiska Annaler: Series B, Human Geography*, 101(2), 118-137.

Wolfgang Bosswick and Friedrich Heckman, (2006). "Integration of Immigrants: Contribution of local and regional authorities". Eurofund, European foundation for the improvement of Living and Working conditions. Retrieved from <http://www.eurofound.europa.eu/pubdocs/2006/22/en/1/ef0622en.pdf> (Accessed on 01/07/2021)

Appendix (A1)

INTERVIEW GUIDE (Non-European immigrants)

The first part of non-European immigrants' interview guide focuses on Age, Gender, living in city or countryside, professions, education, family (How many people, including the interviewee, live in its household), the country of origin, year of arrival in Sweden, the reason of moving to Sweden (Refugee, family reunification/ love, student visa or work visa), Swedish citizenship, and the how interviewee evaluate its own skills in Swedish language. the Second part focuses on Identification that refers to an individual's identification with a social system where the interviewee sees itself as a part of a collective body. Identification has both cognitive and emotional aspects (Heckmann, & Bosswick, 2006). Interviewees are asked about detention of 'being Swedish' and 'integration' and how they are connected to the Swedish society. The third part focuses on non-European immigrants' integration into the Swedish Labuor market, to know how interviewee perceive the obstacles that prevent him/her from integrating into the Swedish labor market and how he/she is economically integrated. The questions try to capture satisfaction with employment situation, and the ability to meet different levels of unexpected expenses (Harder et al, 2018). The fourth part of the interview guide focuses on the non-European immigrants' social integration and their interactive integration which means the acceptance of non-European immigrants in relationships and social networks in the Swedish society (Heckmann & Bosswick, 2006).

Basic Information

- How old are you?
- How do you identify yourself, male female other?
- Do you live in city or countryside?
- What do you do in life? Work study, etc
- You work: Is it full-time or part time job? Do you Work outside the home?
- What is your education level? *Pre-Secondary, Post-Secondary, Bachelor's degree, master's degree, or doctorate*
- Family: How many people, including yourself, live in your household?

- Where do you come from?
- When did you move to Sweden?
- Why did you come to Sweden? *Refugee, family reunification/ love, student visa or work visa?*
- When did you receive your residence permit?
- Do you have a Swedish citizenship? *If not, do you plan on obtaining one?*
- How do you evaluate your own skills in Swedish language? *Poor, pre-intermediate, intermediate, good, very good*

I- Identification

1. What does it mean for you to be Swedish? (*Identification*)
2. To what extent do you personally feel that you are Swedish? (Scale of one to seven) (*Identification*).
3. How would you describe an immigrant who is integrated into the Swedish society? (*Identification*)
4. After receiving your residence permit, did you attend introduction to society course (samhällsorientering)? If yes, do you feel that such courses helped you to get integrated into the Swedish Society? (*Structural integration*)
5. Do you think that immigrant integration in Sweden is a two-way process of mutual adaptation by both non-European immigrants and Swedes? Why? (*Identification*)
6. How connected do you feel with the Swedish society? (*Identification*)
7. How often do you feel like an outsider in Sweden? (*Identification*)

II- Integration into the Swedish labour market

1. How do you see migration impact on Swedish economic growth?
 1. Do you think the Swedish Labour Market is open for non-European immigrants? (*Structural integration*)
 2. How would you describe obstacles that prevent non-European immigrants from integrating into the Swedish labor market?

2. How do you evaluate your satisfaction with your current employment? Is it relevant to your education and previous work experience?
3. What do you think non-European immigrant need to do to get into the Swedish labour market?
3. Did you receive support from The Swedish Public Employment Service (Arbetsförmedlingen) or other actors (Municipalities or NGOs) to find job in Sweden? How do you evaluate this service / support? (*Structural integration*)

II- Social integration

1. What is the percentage of your friends who are born and raised in Sweden? How often do communicate with them? In which activities or events do you meet them? (*Interactive integration*)
2. What is the percentage of your friends who are non-European immigrants? How often do communicate with them? In which activities or events do you meet them? (*Interactive integration*)
3. How can former non-European immigrants impact newly arrived non-European immigrant integration into Swedish society? (*Interactive integration*)
4. Do you think that non-European immigrants can get integrated into the Swedish society without giving up all of their own culture? (*Cultural integration*)
5. In your opinion, as non-European immigrant, what is hindering your social integration into the Swedish society? (*Interactive integration*)
6. How has your social life changed after learning the Swedish language?
7. Do you celebrate Swedish holidays? such as midsummer, Christmas Valborg, Fat Tuesday (fittesdagen) etc. (*Cultural integration*)
8. Have you experienced the feeling that you do not belong neither to the Swedish society nor to your country of origin? (*Identification*)

Appendix (A2) INTERVIEW GUIDE (Swedes)

The first part of Swedes' interview guide focuses on basic information such as, age, gender, living in city or countryside, professions, education, family (How many people, including the interviewee, live in its household), and if one of his/her parents is born outside Sweden. The Second part interviewees are asked about definition of 'being Swedish' and 'integration'. The third part focuses on how interviewee's experience to work with non-European immigrants and who he/she perceive the obstacles that prevent non-European immigrants from integrating into the Swedish labor market. The fourth part focuses on social integration and their daily interactive integration with non-European immigrants.

Basic Information

- How old are you?
- How do you identify yourself, male female other?
- Do you live in city or countryside?
- What do you do in life? Work study, etc
- You work: Is it full-time or part time job? Do you Work outside the home?
- What is your education level? *Pre-Secondary, Post-Secondary, Bachelor's degree, master's degree, or doctorate*
- Family: How many people, including yourself, live in your household?
- Are one or both your parents are born outside of Sweden?
 - *If yes, where?*
 - *If yes, when did your parent come to Sweden?*
 - *Why did they come to Sweden? Refugee, family reunification/love, student visa or work visa?*

I- Identification

1. What does it mean for you to be Swedish? (*Identification*)
2. What does '*integration*' word mean to you? (*Identification*)
3. How would you describe an immigrant who is integrated into the Swedish society?
(*Identification*)

4. Do you think that immigrant integration in Sweden is a two-way process of mutual adaptation by both non-European immigrants and Swedes? Why? (*Identification*)

II- Integration into the Swedish labour market

4. How do you see migration impact on Swedish economic growth?
5. How accessible do you think Swedish Labour Market is for non-European immigrants? (*Structural integration*)
6. Do you work with non-European immigrants or have you in the past?
7. In your opinion, what obstacles that prevent non-European immigrants from integrating into the Swedish labor market? (*Structural integration*)
8. Based on your experience to work with non-European immigrants, what do you think they need to do to meet the Swedish labour market requirement? (*Structural integration*)

III- Social Integration

1. What is the percentage of your friends who are non-European immigrants? How often do communicate with them? In which activities or events do you meet them? (*Interactive integration*)
2. How can former non-European immigrants impact -either positively or negatively- integrating the newly arrived non-European immigrants into Swedish society? (*Interactive integration*)
3. Do you think that it is possible non-European immigrants can be integrated into the Swedish society without giving up all of their own culture? (*Cultural integration*)
4. What is hindering better interaction and integration between non-European immigrants and Swedes in daily life? (*Interactive integration*)
5. Do you participate with non-European immigrants' traditional celebrations? (*Cultural integration*)

Appendix (B1) Non-European Immigrants Respondent list

(MJ-40) (M= Immigrants, J=Respondent J, 40=Years in Sweden)

Respondent		Age	Gender	Country of origin	Occupation	Education	Years in Sweden	Visa Class	City, Town, countryside	Family member	Interview Information
1	(MJ-40)	59	Male	Palestine/ Syria	Work, full time	Secondary	40	Refugee	Lindome	4	Interview was taken in April,2021 face to face, (In Arabic). The duration was 56 minutes. Transcription length is 12 pages. (Arabic & English)
2	(MK-35)	66	Male	Iran	Work full time	Master's degree	35	Refugee	Angared	2	Interview was taken in April,2021 face to face. (In English). The duration was 49 minutes. Transcription length is 11 pages. (English)
3	(ML-34)	59	Male	Palestine/ Lebanon	Work full time	Master's degree	34	Love	Göteborg	1	Interview was taken in April,2021 on Zoom, (In Arabic). The duration was 62 minutes. Transcription length is 10 pages. (Arabic & English)
4	(MM- 33)	56	Femal	Lebanon	Work full time	Post-Secondary	33	Refugee	Göteborg	2	Interview was taken in April,2021 on Zoom, (In Arabic). The duration was 35 minutes. Transcription length is 7 pages. (Arabic & English)
5	(MN-19)	48	Male	Iraq	Work full time		19	Refugee	Lund	1	Interview was taken in April,2021 on Zoom. (In English). The duration was 31 minutes. Transcription length is 7 pages. (English)
6	(MO-15)	24	Male	Somalia	Work full time / Study part time	Bachelor's degree	15	Family reunification	Göteborg	3	Interview was taken in April,2021 face to face . (In English). The duration was 33 minutes. Transcription length is 9 pages. (English)
7	(MP-9)	42	Femal	Indonesia	Work full time	Bachelor's degree	9	Refugee	Stockholm	4	Interview was taken in April,2021 via Zoom. (In English). The duration was 30 minutes. Transcription length is 7 pages. (English)
8	(MQ-9)	38	Femal	Sudan	Job seeker	Doctorate	9	Student Visa	Nörköping	1	Interview was taken in April,2021 on Zoom. (In Arabic). duration was 35 minutes. Transcription length is 12 pages. (Arabic & English)
9	(MR-7)	35	Femal	Tunisia	Work full time	Master's degree	7	Refugee	Mölnadal	4	Interview was taken in April,2021 on Zoom. (In Arabic). The duration was 44 minutes. Transcription length is 14 pages. (Arabic & English)

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10	(MS-7)	45	Femal	Jordan	Job seeker	Master's degree	7	Refugee	Göteborg	3	Interview was taken in April,2021 on Zoom. (In Arabic). The duration was 35 minutes. Transcription length is 7 pages. (Arabic & English)
11	(MT-7)	24	Male	Afghanistan	Student	Post-Secondary	7	Refugee	Partille	3	Interview was taken in April,2021 on Zoom (In English). The duration was 33 minutes. Transcription length is 9 pages. (English)
12	(MU-7)	57	Femal	Syria	Job seeker	Bachelor's degree	7	Refugee	Uddevala	2	Interview was taken in April,2021 on Messenger. (In Arabic). The duration was 35 minutes. Transcription length is 12 pages. (Arabic & English)
13	(MV-6)	32	Female	Gaza Strip	Work part time Study part time	Bachelor's degree	6	Refugee	Vänersborg	3	Interview was taken in April,2021 via Zoom. (In English). duration was 36 minutes. Transcription length is 9 pages. (English)
14	(MW-5)	30	Male	Syria	Work full time	Pre-Secondary	5	Reugee	Varberg	2	Interview was taken in April,2021 on Zoom. (In Arabic). The duration was 37 minutes. Transcription length is 10 pages. (Arabic & English)
15	(MX-4)	38	Male	Iran	Job seeker & Run his own business,IT branch	Master's degree	4	Student Visa	Göteborg	1	Interview was taken in April,2021 on Zoom. (In English). The duration was 39 minutes. Transcription length is 10 pages. (English)
16	(MY-2)	37	Male	Yemen	Job seeker	Bachelor's degree	2	Refugee	Rävlanda	5	Interview was taken in April,2021 on Zoom. (In Arabic). The duration was 50 minutes. Transcription length is 12pages. (Arabic ,English)

Appendix (B2) Swedes Respondent list

(SA-65): (S= Swede, A=Respondent A, 65=Age)

Respondents		Age	Gender	Occupation	Education	Parents	City, town, countryside	Family member	Interview Information
1	(SA-65)	65	Male	Retired	Master's degree	His father moved from Russia, 1922, as a refugee	Lerum	2	Interview was taken in April,2021 face to face and duration was 24 minutes. Transcription length is 6 pages in English.
2	(SB-61)	61	Female	Work	Bachelor's degree	Both	Stenungsund	1	Interview was taken in April,2021 on Zoom and duration was 34 minutes. Transcription length is 8 pages in English.
3	(SC-50)	50	Female	Work	Master's degree	Both	Malmö	4	Interview was taken in May,2021 on Zoom and duration was 44 minutes. Transcription length is 12 pages in English.
4	(SD-39)	39	Male	Work	Doctorate	His father moved from Germany, 1951, for work reason	Alingsås	4	Interview was taken in May,2021 face to face and duration was 31 minutes. Transcription length is 9 pages in English.
5	(SE-38)	38	Female	Work	Master's degree	Both	Stockholm	2	Interview was taken in April,2021 on Zoom and duration was 33 minutes. Transcription length is 9 pages in English.
6	(SF-34)	34	Female	Work/ Study	Bachelor's degree	Her father moved from Finland, 1953, for work reason	Göteborg	2	Interview was taken in April,2021 on Zoom and duration was 42 minutes. Transcription length is 7 pages in English.
7	(SG-27)	27	Male	Work	Master's degree	Both	Göteborg	2	Interview was taken in April,2021 on Zoom and duration was 30 minutes. Transcription length is 7 pages. (English)
8	(SH-27)	27	Male	Work/ Study	Master's degree	His Mother moved from Vietnam, 1980s, as a refugee	Göteborg	2	Interview was taken in May,2021 on Zoom and duration was 34 minutes. Transcription length is 7 pages in English.
9	(SI-23)	23	Female	Work/ Study	Bachelor's degree	Her Mother moved from New Zealand, 2000, for love reason	Stockholm	1	Interview was taken in May,2021 on Zoom and duration was 30 minutes. Transcription length is 8 pages in English.